

PROJECT READING ENHANCEMENT ACTIVITIES FOR SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN (REACH): ITS EFFECTS TO THE READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS OF GRADE V LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the effect of Project Reading Enhancement Activities for school-age Children (REACH) on the reading comprehension skills of Grade 5 learners of Bayanihan Elementary School, San Pascual North District, Division of Masbate Province for the School Year 2023-2024. It answered (1) the learners' reading comprehension skills before project REACH implementation; (2) the design of the reading intervention; (3) the curricular validity of the reading intervention design along with face, content and construct; (4) the reading comprehension skills after project REACH implementation; (5) significant difference of the learners' reading comprehension skills before and after project REACH implementation; (6) significant relationship between the reading comprehension skills before and after the implementation of Project REACH and the reading intervention design; (7) extent of influence of project REACH to the reading comprehension skills of the learners. The study applied descriptive-comparative-correlational and research and development methods. There were 50 grade 5 learner-respondents officially enrolled in Bayanihan Elementary School, San Pascual North District, Division of Masbate Province. The main gathering tools used was teacher-made test. To treat the data, frequency count, percentage technique, mean, standard deviation, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation of Coefficient, Coefficient of Determination and t-test were applied. Findings revealed were: (1) the level of learners' reading comprehension skills before project REACH implementation was 61.63; (2) The intervention program to improve the reading comprehension skills of grade 5 learners followed the following design: objective, content, learning activities and assessment.; (3) the curricular validity along face obtained an average weighted mean of 3.98; content on average weighted mean of 3.98; and construct an average weighted average of 3.96. the overall average weighted mean was 3.97 (4) the overall reading comprehension skills was 67.91 ; (5) significant difference of the learners' reading comprehension skills before

and after project REACH implementation obtained a t-value of -9.482 and a p-value of 0.000; (6) the significant relationship between the reading comprehension skills that the learners developed after project REACH was given by the r-value of 0.944 and a p-value of 0.000; (7) Project REACH extent of influence on the reading comprehension skills of the learners was given by the r^2 – value of 0.891. Conclusion drawn were: (1) the overall reading comprehension skills was emerging.; (2) Any intervention program followed a design; (3) the curricular validity for the reading intervention along face, content and construct was highly valid. (4) overall reading comprehension skills was emerging; (5) There was a significant difference on the learners' reading comprehension skills before and after project REACH implementation.; (6) There was a significant relationship between the reading comprehension skills of the learners before and after project REACH implementation; (7) Project REACH has high influence on the reading comprehension skills of the learners.

Keywords: *Reading Enhancement, Reading Comprehension, Reading Skills, Learners*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is the most valuable skill that a person should learn to have. It adds worth to someone's identity. A person is somewhat unimportant when he does not know how to read and write. Communication between two persons will not succeed when the recipient does not know how to read the text from the sender. Reading is the interpretation of the written texts. It is also a version of signs and letters sent by the sender. However, reading is not the end of the interpretation of text and symbols without proper comprehension by the individual. Comprehension is the reason for reading. If readers can read the words but do not understand or connect to what they are reading, they are not really reading. Good readers are both purposeful and active, and have the skills to absorb what they read, analyze it, make sense of it and make it their own.

Students reading comprehension is one of the most prevalent issues that our educational system is currently facing. Most of the learners could hardly understand what they are reading. Reading comprehension is the most important in the basic education among the learners especially elementary pupils. The state of education in the Philippines demands immediate attention and commitment to improvement so we can give our children the best learning experience that they deserve.

Further, to strengthen the reading proficiency of every learner and to nurture a culture of reading which is a requisite skill in all content areas, the Department of Education supports Every Child a Reader Program which seeks to equip learners with reading skills appropriate to the grade level she is enrolled. They even funded the necessary expenses for reading literacy initiatives in every school. Teachers who are involved in implementing reading interventions beyond their six-hour actual teaching load

were also granted service credit equivalent to one day. As a result, commencing School Year 2018-2019, the DepEd continued to deliver the Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) assessment to learners in public schools countrywide through the Bureau of Learning Delivery-Teaching and Learning Division.

Additionally, anchored on the Every Child A Reader Program and to address the non-readers problem among Bicolano learners from Grade 1 to Senior High School, the department launched the 5B's, "Bawat Batang Bicolano Bihasang Bumasa" which aimed to equip Bicolano learners with strategic reading and writing skills to make them independent young readers and writers.

Unfortunately, amidst the Department of Education's efforts and initiatives to further enhance the educational system here in the Philippines, still it was not enough based on the results of the national assessments for students reading. The overview of DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019 states that:

"There are still many early grade learners struggling to meet the learning standards in early language, literacy and numeracy. Low achievement levels in English, Math and Science appear to be caused by gaps in learners' comprehension. This means that there are many low performing learners who could not comprehend (read and understand) Math and Science word problems that are written in English."

Moreover, the Philippines slip from 20th to 27th place in 2020's English Proficiency Index. According to research released in 2020 by English First, a Swiss company, the country dropped seven points in global ranking. The data also revealed that since 2016, the country's ranking had been badly declining. The Philippine dropped from 13th place in 2016, to 15th place in 2017, 14th in 2018 and 20th place in 2019. In the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics in 2019, the Philippines was also ranked in the bottom half of the six countries in reading, mathematics, and writing literacy (ABS-CBN News, 2021).

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) in 2022, reported that the Philippines was ranked as among the lowest performers among the 81 countries the Philippines ranked 79th. The country had an average reading score of 347 or Level 1a, which was 100 points lower than the OECD average of 472 or Level 2.

This study was anchored on DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019 entitled Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs Initiative which aimed to make every learner a proficient reader). Schools across the country are tasked to help learners develop their reading skills. Similarly, this study was based on DEped Order No. 12, s. 2017 in

reference to Deped Order No. 12, s. 2015 entitled Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP). This program aimed to develop Filipino learners' reading skills.

In Bayanihan Elementary School, the school where the researcher teaches, not all learners knew how to read which were all shown in the conducted Reading Literacy Assessment (RLA) which the data showed an alarming result. Out of 50 learners, 15 or 30% fell under Established Level; 18 or 36% as Emerging Level, 2 or 4% as Coping level and 15 or 30% as Deficit Level.

Schools around the country had been tasked to help learners strengthen their reading skills and encourage young learners to develop their interest in reading. Due to the prevalent issues on reading comprehension skills, this study focuses on determining the effect of Project Reading Enhancement Activities for school-age Children (REACH) on the reading comprehension skills of grade 5 learners in Bayanihan Elementary School, San Pascual North District, Division of Masbate Province, School Year 2023-2024 with a view to suggesting ways in which the intervention can be better implemented bearing in mind the numerous challenges schools have on the ground in order to enhance reading comprehension of grade 5 learners.

Research Questions

This study determined the effect of the Project Reading Enhancement Activities for school-age Children (REACH) on the reading comprehension skills of Grade 5 learners, Bayanihan Elementary School, San Pascual North District, Division of Masbate, School Year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of the reading comprehension skills of the learners in terms of:
 - a. Word Recognition;
 - b. Fluency; and
 - c. Comprehension?
2. What is the design of the reading intervention to improve the reading comprehension skills of the learners in terms of:
 - a. Objectives;
 - b. Content;
 - c. Learning activities;
 - d. Assessment?
3. What is the curricular validity for the reading intervention design along with:
 - a. Face;

- b. Content; and
 - c. Construct?
4. What is the level of the reading comprehension of the learners after Project REACH was implemented?
 5. Is there a significant difference on the reading comprehension skills before and after Project REACH implementation?
 6. Is there a significant relationship between the reading comprehension skills after Project REACH was implemented and the reading intervention design?
 7. To what extent does the Project REACH influence the reading comprehension skills of the learners?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the over-all framework and methodology that the researcher used in the conduct of the study. This includes the method of data analysis, respondents of the study, data gathering procedure, procedure of investigation and the statistical tools used in treating the data gathered.

Methods Used

In this study, descriptive-comparative-correlational and research and development methods of research were used. Descriptive method was used to determine the comprehension skills of the respondents in terms of word recognition, fluency and comprehension that the pupils developed before and after Project REACH was implemented. The comparative method was employed to determine the significant difference in the comprehension level of pupils before and after Project REACH implementation.

Correlational method was utilized to determine the significant relationship between the comprehension skills that the pupils developed before and after project REACH was implemented.

Research and Development method was utilized in crafting the reading intervention design to improve the reading comprehension skills of the learners in terms of word recognition, fluency and comprehension. Likewise, the same method was used in determining the influence of Project REACH on the reading comprehension skills of the learners.

Respondents of the Study

This study employed fifty (50) grade 5 learners who were officially enrolled at Bayanihan Elementary School, San Pascual North. Total enumeration was used to identify the respondents of the study; hence no sampling technique was applied.

Data Gathering Tools

Research findings were based on the data gathered, and their validity and reliability were affected by the quality of the research instruments used. To ensure quality information, it is expedient that the data collected was with the use of appropriate instruments so that the drawing of inferences and making decisions was considered informative and factual.

Teacher-made test. The researcher developed a teacher-made test together with the table of specifications. It was validated by the master teachers with a weighted mean of 4.43 resulted as excellent. Thus, it was used to determine the comprehension skills of grade 5 learners in terms of word recognition, fluency and comprehension before and after project REACH implementation on the covered specific most essential learning competencies in the first and second quarters in English 5 particularly reading comprehension. The teacher-made test undergone validation by the experts in the field who taught English for a long time. A dry-run of the teacher-made test was administered to selected grade 5 learners in San Pascual Central School, San Pascual North District that were not the actual respondents of the study.

The test was 30-item consisting reading comprehension questions. It was administered to the learners to determine the word recognition and fluency level of the learners. Thus, the teacher-made test went through reliability and validity test using Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 and item analysis, test item to determine the index of difficulty and index of discrimination of the test. The results were highly reliable and valid.

The following descriptors were utilized to evaluate the learners' level of reading comprehension before and after project REACH implementation. These were based on the scale in the learners' Rapid Literacy Assessment indicated in Regional Memorandum No. 363, s. 2023, also known as "Guidelines in the Administration of Rapid Literacy Assessment for Grade 4-12 Learners in Region V."

80-100	Established (Es)
50-79	Emerging (Em)
30-49	Coping (C)
0-29	Deficit (D)

Evaluation Checklist. This looked like a form or structured document, the design is similar to a questionnaire to gather feedback, opinions, or assessments on various aspects of the parts of the reading intervention design. It was evaluated by the expert in the field with a weighted mean of 3.97 resulted as highly valid. This was used to measure the quality of the reading intervention design. This consisted of a series of statements or questions with rating scales. The questions or statements were carefully crafted to elicit specific information from the respondents, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the reading intervention design as being evaluated. Moreover, this had the following purposes: assess the quality of the reading intervention design, gather feedback from English teachers who were experts in the field, evaluate the effectiveness of the developed reading intervention design. This played a vital role in identifying the strengths and weaknesses and understanding needs for improvements. This believed to help the researcher indirectly improved the learners' reading comprehension skills. The results obtained were subjected to descriptive statistics to better analyze and interpret the data for a positive decision. The following descriptors were used to interpret the responses of the respondents.

Scale	Value		Verbal Interpretation
4	3.76 - 4.00	-	Highly Valid (HV)
3	2.51 - 3.75	-	Moderately Valid (HV)
2	1.76 – 2.50	-	Less Valid (LV)
1	1.00 – 1.75	-	Least Valid (LstV)

Procedures of Investigation

To come up with a reliable result of the study, the researcher followed a step-by-step procedure. The researcher's first action was to define and identify the study's problem. Following the establishment of the problem and the identification of the significant variables, the researcher gathered pertinent literature and studies to support the objectives. This gave the study a more focused direction. Next, the respondents and the statistical tools appropriate for the research problems were identified.

Conceptualization of the Research Problem. The researcher initially determines the purpose of the study, the methodology, and the topics that will be addressed. The researcher then intended to choose pertinent sources and create queries that could yield reliable responses. Following that, a data analysis plan was created using a variety of statistical techniques.

Approval of the Research Title. After the completion of the title proposal, the researcher secured the approval of the research proposal from the thesis committee of the School of Graduate Studies.

Securing Permit to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the School Head, Public Schools District Supervisor of San Pascual North District and Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd Masbate Province. A letter request was submitted to the School Head of Bayanihan Elementary School and San Pascual Central School, asking permission to conduct the study to the learners.

Preparation of Data Gathering Tools. The data gathering tools that was used in the conduct of this study was the teacher-made test. The teacher-made test was used to collect data about the grade 5 reading comprehension skills in terms of word recognition, fluency and comprehension.

Validation of the Data Gathering Tools. The teacher-made test was validated by experts in the field who taught English for a long time. After the validation, questions which needed changes were changed.

Evaluation of the Data Gathering Tools. The teacher-made test was evaluated by the experts in the field.

Dry-Run of the Teacher-Made Test. Teacher-made test was assessed through validity and reliability. The tool was validated by means of pilot testing to grade 5 learners of San Pascual Central School who were not part of the school as the main respondents of this study. Consequently, the teacher-made test was revised after it was pilot-tested considering the result in item analysis. The table of specification was updated as the tool was revised and finalized for the administration of the teacher-made test.

Administration of the Data Gathering Tools. After approval of the request to conduct the study, the researcher explained personally to the respondents the goal of the study and asked for their voluntary and sincere participation. The teacher-made test was administered on a specific date and time. The teacher-made test was administered to the grade 5 learners within an hour. After administering the test, the questionnaires were retrieved. All participants' names and scores were retained and used exclusively for the study's purposes.

Implementation of the intervention. The researcher implemented the intervention program which is Project REACH (Reading Enhancement Activities for School-age Children). It was implemented by the researcher for 8-weeks.

Processing of Data Gathered. The data was gathered, tabulated, analyzed, discussed, and interpreted carefully according to the assigned statistical treatment and computations.

Writing of the research report. After the data were organized, analyzed, and interpreted, the researcher prepared the research report which was subjected to a series of revisions and improvements. The collaborative discussion between the researcher and her research adviser was key in finalizing the study output and thesis.

Submission of the manuscripts. After thorough revisions and refinement, the research report was presented to the Graduate Studies panel of examiners.

Statistical Tools

The researcher utilized the following statistical tools to come up with acceptable and valid results of the study. Computation was done online.

Mean. The mean was used in determining the level of reading comprehension skills of the learner-respondents.

Standard Deviation. This tool was used to determine the extent of variability or dispersion of the scores of the learners in the reading comprehension level. It described the homogeneity and heterogeneity of the scores.

Proficiency Level. This was used to determine the reading comprehension skills of the learners based on their responses from the teacher-made test.

Pearson Product -Moment Correlation of Coefficient. This was used to measure the significant relationship between the comprehension skills before and after project REACH was implemented.

Coefficient of Determination. This was employed to assess influence, or contribution of the independent variable (x) to the dependent variable (y). In this study, coefficient of determination was used to determine the percentage of influence of Project REACH implementation to the reading comprehension of learners.

Paired t-test. This was used to treat the level of validity of the proposed intervention to improve the reading comprehension skills of the learners.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section is a discussion of the results of the study. Data were placed in tabular form to facilitate analysis and discussion.

Reading Comprehension Skills of the Learners

One of the indispensable roles of teachers in primary education is to improve learners' comprehension skills on reading. This function drives the teachers' competent and innovative efforts to adopt or employ effective strategies in honing pupils' interests in reading. The reading comprehension skills of the learners were measured in terms of word recognition, fluency, and comprehension. The result of the comprehension skills of the learners is presented in Table 1 with respective items, mean, standard deviation, the performance level of learners and corresponding verbal interpretation.

Based from the data, the level of comprehension skills of grade 5 learners on word recognition was 87.30 which ranked first, fluency ranked second with 63.66, while the lowest percentage of 33.92 was on comprehension. The overall mean of the learners along the aspects tested was 61.63 interpreted as Emerging.

Table 1
Level of Reading Comprehension of the Learners

Aspects	SD	Ave. Grade	Int.	Rank
Word Recognition	8.86	87.30	Es	1
Fluency	19.72	63.66	Em	2
Comprehension	18.85	33.92	C	3
Overall Average Grade		61.63	Em	

Legend: 80-100 - Established (Es)
 50-79 – Emerging (Em) SD – Standard Deviation
 30-49 – Coping (C) Int. - Interpretation
 0-29 – Deficit (D)

It can be inferred that the results of the level of reading comprehension skills of grade 5 learners in the assessment given along with word recognition, fluency and comprehension showed that learners were not yet Grade Level Ready. It can be gleaned from the table that word recognition got the highest percentage because it was easy to master, followed by fluency and the comprehension. Comprehension got the lowest percentage because it requires higher level of understanding. These results were in consonance with the study of Martin (2020) which stated that reading comprehension is

the capacity to read texts quickly and effectively for meaning. Children learnt it as the last stage of the reading process after mastering phonics, fluency and vocabulary.

This study was anchored on Barlette's Schema Theory where learners used their previous skills in reading and remember the phonemic awareness and alphabetic principles. Hence learners were given learning activities that fit their level. Learners who were still in word recognition, the activities given to them were also at this level same as fluency and comprehension.

Word Recognition. Word recognition skill is the first step an individual takes to read. It is imperative that people learn to recognize words accurately during the reading process because reading cannot be done without word recognition. Word recognition alone, however, is insufficient. One could argue that the initial step in deciphering written language is word recognition. There were 82 words in this aspect reflected in the teacher-made test which was the basis of determining the level of comprehension skills in terms of word recognition. It was the percentage of words correctly read over the total number of words in a given passage.

Thus, it can be gleaned that the result attained by learners during the assessment in word recognition showed a mean of 87.30 interpreted as Established and a proficiency level of 1.06 with a standard deviation of 8.86. Considering the learners' grade level, this was not acceptable because this aspect was in the lower level in reading comprehension skills. It can be inferred that not all the learners were able to decode because as readers become increasingly proficient decoders, automatic word recognition develops and also learners were not exposed into words.

These results were supported by the findings of Perfetti (2017), that visual word recognition, or the ability to recall word representations from memory, is a cornerstone of reading and learning in school. When a child is presented with a string of letters, the first process is to decode the letters to the spoken form. If a word has been successfully decoded, it can be recognized as familiar (seen or heard before) with greater speed. Word recognition is possible without word identification (recall of meaning and encountered contexts, since word recognition can take place by recognizing trained pseudowords as familiar or by only having a vague sense of familiarity after having heard a word once or twice. Consequently, exposure has repeatedly been shown to be a significant predictor of word recognition (Marelli, 2017).

Fluency. Fluency is a critical factor in literacy success. It is important because it builds a bridge between word recognition and comprehension. Because fluency is needed to be a successful reader, it is vital that educators measure reading rates regularly.

The teacher-made test particularly a passage developed by the researcher that were used to determine the level of comprehension skills in terms of fluency was composed of 82 words. Additionally, the teacher-made test results were presented in Table 1 which contains the aspects together with the scale and corresponding descriptors based on the Guidelines on the administration of Rapid Literacy Assessment.

As reflected in Table 1, the result of the level of the learners' reading comprehension skills in term of fluency resulted to a mean of 63.66 interpreted as Emerging and with a standard deviation of 19.72. It can be deduced that learners in grade 5 were not fluent reader because readers who have not yet developed fluency read slowly word by word. Their oral reading is choppy and lacks prosody. It was supported by the study of Acosta-Tello (2019), which stated that "Without fluency, children are basically decoders who are able to decipher what the letters in a word say, letter by letter, or syllable by syllable, and who can then hopefully recognize what the word means". Similarly, when fluently reading, children quickly decode words and simultaneously gather meaning from the sentences to develop an understanding of the story's content. They no longer focus on decoding individual words, but rather read sentences smoothly and focus on comprehending the story. This fluent reading enables students to ask and answer comprehension questions as well as make their own personal connections (Paige, 2020).

Likewise, the study of Ates (2019) stated that fluent reading has many benefits associated with it other than being able to read at an adequate rate. These positive outcomes can be vocabulary outcome, phonemic awareness, and comprehension of stories among other literacy components.

Comprehension. All other academic abilities rest on a strong foundation of reading comprehension. It aids in vocabulary development, world education, and the understanding of difficult ideas in children. Proficiency in reading comprehension is a prerequisite for academic success. Strong reading comprehension abilities increase a child's chances of success in both school and in life.

The learner's level of reading comprehension skill in terms of comprehension was determined through the 30-item teacher-made test developed by the researcher where learners obtained an average grade of 33.92 interpreted as Coping with a Standard Deviation of 18.85. The standard deviation indicated that the pupils were not in the same level in terms of comprehension skills. Some got it, but majority did not.

As shown in the result, it can be inferred that the grade 5 learners struggled in reading comprehension because learners were not able to master the lower skills in reading comprehension. This finding was parallel to the findings of Martin (2020) that reading comprehension is the capacity to read text quickly and effectively for meaning.

Children learnt it as the last stage of the reading process after mastering phonics, fluency and vocabulary. Furthermore, the findings of Hung (2015), states that reading comprehension is a dynamic process between the written symbols and the understanding of the context behind the symbols and the discovery of the link between words and concepts. On the other hand, the findings of Lervag (2018) stated that reading comprehension and word decoding are the two major determinants of the development of reading comprehension. On the same point of view, the study of Silawi et al., (2020) emphasized that reading comprehension has three components, which are process strategies (word recognition), prior knowledge and conceptual abilities.

Design of the Reading Intervention

Project Reading Enhancement Activities for school age Children (REACH) was an Eight-Week tutorial class which allotted 45-minute time thrice a week, from 3:45 to 4:30 in the afternoon at Bayanihan Elementary School, Kindergarten Classroom during Mondays, Wednesdays, and Fridays. Tutorial is an effective way to improve the reading comprehension skills of the learners.

Parallel to the findings of Mckay (2016) which states that students who attend tutorials have 20% improvement in their marks. Likewise, students who attend tutorial had better academic performance than those who did not attend at all. Likewise, Salazar et al. (2014) revealed that the tutoring program had a favorable impact on the students' classes, noting that the grades of students who had one-on-one tutoring were statistically different from those of the students who did not attend tutorial classes. Tutorials are well-appreciated by the students too.

This study was anchored on Vygotskys Theory of the "Zone of Proximal Development". This theory puts forward that a learner can enhance his/her cognitive level and he/she is able to achieve this on his/her own capacity by responding to questions and learning with a "more capable peer" or a teacher.

For a tutoring program to be effective, it should be planned and adapted to the context and the needs and interests of the students (Lemus, et al.,2015).

The design of the reading intervention to improve the reading comprehension skills of the learners was measured through a set of parameters such as: objectives; content; learning activities; and assessment.

Objectives. It refers to the objectives or competencies that they need to master based on their level. This provides *clear and concise way to define what to achieve*. These were the competencies that must be achieved or mastered by the learners during the

hands-on activities. Instead of focusing on what the teacher will cover or do during the activity, objectives should be learner-centered and should outline what the learners should be able to accomplish as a result of instruction. In this study, the objectives of project REACH were the following: decrease the number of struggling readers in Grade 5; improve the reading comprehension skills in terms of word recognition, fluency and comprehension; and establish a harmonious relationship for the learners to appreciate reading comprehension

Content. These were the subject matters which focused on the learners reading comprehension skills in terms of word recognition, fluency and comprehension. These were the competencies needed by each learner to gain high level of mastery in reading comprehension. In this study, the focused lessons were for word recognition, fluency and comprehension.

Learning activities. Learning activities are the practice reading exercises given to the learners for them to develop the different comprehension skills. It includes activities that can develop their speed in reading and comprehension skills. Timed or speed reading can help learners enhance their fluency. Learners read under time constraints to improve their reading pace and beat prior personal records. Provide learners with reading activities that can encourage them to think logically and abstractly. It also includes various challenging activities, and it was divided into three parts such as activity for word recognition, fluency, and comprehension. Learners were group into two. Different activities were given in each group.

Word recognition activity that was utilized in this study was spelling. The first group of learners was given set of words for them to read and study in advance. Every day, they were tasked to read 10 words and they must spell it during tutorial time. Sometimes, they were tasked to spell it orally one by one. The teacher did not allow learners to stop the task unless they spelled all the words correctly. The second group had also spelling but the words to be spelled were from the passage that were given to them.

One of the fluency activities was one-one-one instruction. Parallel with the study of Hudson (2020), it suggested that elementary students with reading difficulties benefit most from one-on-one instructions. The time spent working on specific, targeted interventions increased the students' overall literacy skills in terms of their fluency rates and comprehension levels. Hence, the research of Craddock (2014) revealed that one-on-one tutoring is a useful pedagogical tool. Another activity for fluency that was implemented and applied was one-minute timed reading. Learners were given reading passage and they read it in a one-minute time, if they cannot do it, they will have to try it again until they were able to do it. Similar with the findings of Kostewicz and Kubina (2020) which articulated that to improve reading fluency students were given a one-minute timed reading assessment and students read each part as many times as they

were able in one minute before moving onto the next part. Students worked their way to the end of the text in the same fashion. The continuous repetition of each part resulted in an increase in student fluency rates. Furthermore, the findings of Hudson et al. (2020) states that regardless of the intervention chosen, they must intentionally support student progress in oral reading fluency. With targeted fluency interventions, students are able to practice reading in a comfortable environment where they can find success and make progress in their fluency rates.

Comprehension activities include signal words and story mats. This activity helped the learners think about and reflect on the most important information in the story. Having them sort the who, what, where, and when of a story helped the learners understand what they are reading that much more and reinforce their knowledge. Explicit teaching, applying variety of reading strategies and pre-reading strategies can also improve reading comprehension skills of the learners. It was also supported by the findings of Ness (2016) that suggest that teachers should adopt explicit teaching style in reading comprehension during reading activities to promote effective reading in students and their effect on enhancing their level of reading comprehension. Students' problems with reading comprehension can be solved by employing a variety of reading strategies. Similarly, Mousavian and Shiahpoosh (2018) proved that effective reading strategies are an effective means to support students in their academics. Students provided with effective reading strategies outperformed the students who were not provided with any pre-reading strategy during comprehension activity.

Assessment. Assessment aids in identifying the tasks required to fulfill the objectives of the project. This assessment helps identify targeted strategies and prioritize resources, which in turn informs the plan and approaches of a project. In this study, assessment was divided into three parts such as assessment for word recognition, fluency and comprehension. For word recognition test, learners were given passage to read and the teacher identify the miscues in oral reading. For the fluency test, learners were tasked to read the passage with specific number of words and the teacher recorded the number of words that the learners read per minute. For the comprehension, learners answered the questions based from the passage being read.

It is very important that a reading intervention design should include assessment because it allows the teacher to monitor learners' progress throughout the implementation of the program. It can also provide with a better understanding of where the learners are going to in the program. Based on this information, teachers can use assessment to reevaluate and modify teaching strategies and to identify any obstacles, real or imagined, that learners may be encountering as a result of the assessment decisions.

Curricular Validity of the Reading Intervention Design

Any developed material should undergo validation by the expert in the field. This is to ensure that the developed material conformed with the standard and it should be reliable and valid. The curricular validity of the reading intervention was based on face, content, and construct.

Face. Table 2A shows the curricular validity of the reading intervention design in terms of its face. Among its indicators, layout and design are simple and easily recognizable; illustrations clarify and supplement the text and font style and size were appropriate to the target users obtained the highest weighted mean 4.00 noted as highly valid. Meanwhile, spaces between words and letters facilitates reading and are attractive

Table 2A
Curricular Validity of the Reading Intervention Design
along with Face

Indicators	Wm	I	Rank
Layout and design are simple and easily recognizable	4.00	HV	2
Illustrations clarify and supplement the text	4.00	HV	2
Font style and size are appropriate for the target users	4.00	HV	2
Spaces between words and letters facilitate reading	3.95	HV	4.5
Attractive and appealing to learners	3.95	HV	4.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.98	HV	

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00 – *Highly Valid (HV)*

2.51 – 3.25 – *Moderately Valid (MV)*

1.76 – 2.50 – *Less Valid (LV)*

1.00 – 1.75 – *Least Valid LSV)*

SD- Standard Deviation

Wm- Weighted Mean

I- Interpretation

and appealing to learners received the lowest weighted mean of 3.95 interpreted as highly valid. However, the overall circular validity for face got an average weighted mean of 3.98 interpreted as highly valid among the respondents.

It implied that all the evaluators have the same way of looking at the three indicators, same evaluation with regards to the first three indicators. However, as regards the two indicators, though they were noted the lowest but statistically, they were interpreted as highly valid. Providing learners with reading intervention with clear instructions can help them ensure that they fully understand what needs to be done to achieve the goal. This finding was supported by Anggraeni et al. (2020) who stated that creating effective, high-quality learning activities begins with adherence to an explicit design process. The activity should also be evaluated to identify ways to improve it for future use.

Content. Table 2B shows the curricular validity of the reading intervention design along content. Among the indicators, the language used is appropriate to the developmental level of the target users; contributes to the achievement of the lesson objectives; and free from prejudices and biases based on ideology, culture, religion, race and gender obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.00 interpreted as highly valid. Meanwhile, develop the learners higher order thinking skills; and integrates across other learning areas, both got the lowest weighted mean of 3.95

Table 2B
Curricular Validity of the Reading Intervention Design
along with Content

Indicators	Wm	I	Rank
The language used is appropriate to the developmental level of the target users	4.00	HV	2
Contributes to the achievement of the lesson objectives	4.00	HV	2
Free from prejudices and biases based on ideology, culture, religion, race and gender	4.00	HV	2
Develop the learners higher order thinking skills	3.95	HV	4.5
Integrates across other learning areas	3.95	HV	4.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.98	HV	

yet were also interpreted as highly valid. The over-all curricular validity of the reading intervention design in terms of content showed an average weighted mean of 3.98 interpreted as highly valid

It can be inferred that the first three indicators under content, were of equal importance based on the evaluation of the validators. It meant that the reading intervention design's content are carefully constructed following both the validation's system concepts and standard format. According to Galanis et al. (2015), comprehensive content, valuable resources, engaging, clear directions throughout the course, and the facility to engage with their teacher(s) to raise concerns and acquire feedback to help the learners learn.

Construct. Table 2C shows the curricular validity of the reading intervention design along construct.

Table 2C
Curricular Validity of the Reading Intervention Design
along with Construct

Indicators	Wm	I	Rank
The presentation is clear, captivating, and understandable	4.00	HV	2
The flow of ideas is smooth and logical	4.00	HV	2
The length of sentences is appropriate to the comprehension level of the target users	4.00	HV	2
Directions are clear and easy to follow	3.90	HV	4.5
Learning activities are adaptive to the learners' level of understanding	3.90	HV	4.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.96	HV	

It was revealed that the first three indicators obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.00 interpreted as highly valid. Meanwhile, the two last indicators got the lowest weighted mean of 3.90 interpreted also as highly valid.

Reading Comprehension Skills of the Learners after Project REACH was implemented

The practice of reading program has been in the limelight for a long time in the Philippine education sector. In fact, the elementary schools in the country devised their own remedial reading programs to assist struggling readers. Table 3 presents the level of learners' reading comprehension skill after Project REACH implementation.

Table 3
Level of Reading Comprehension of the Learners
After Project REACH Implementation

Aspects	SD	Ave. Grade	Int.	Rank
Word Recognition	5.92	90.64	Es	1
Fluency	18.47	68.02	Em	2
Comprehension	16.55	45.08	C	3
Overall Average Grade		67.91	Em	

Legend: 80-100 - Established (Es)
 50-79 – Emerging (Em)
 30-49 – Coping (C)
 0-29 – Deficit (D)

SD – Standard Deviation
Int. - Interpretation

Word Recognition. Word recognition skills are crucial in reading. They are indicators of reading fluency and are very important to monitor the progress and development of the level of learning of an individual. Word recognition skills can lead to better reading comprehension when further improved. The acquisition and development of word recognition involve multiple factors and processes. It plays a vital role for the success in reading comprehension. Therefore, word recognition skills are essential for reading proficiency and should be emphasized in literacy interventions.

It was revealed in the table that the result attained by the learners during the post-test assessment in the word recognition showed a mean of 90.64 interpreted as established. Based from the result, there were changes from the data of word recognition. It can be inferred that the activities given during the intervention were effective.

Hence, these results were parallel to the findings of Buncag (2020) who claimed that reading enhancement interventions are considered part of education with its mission of pulling up the students and leading them on the right track. It is considered as a rapidly growing method of saving the students on the fall of their learnings. Additionally, the study of Jiang (2016) states that reading activities and tasks would improve the learners' comprehension skills. Moreover, Abana (2020) states that remedial program is an answer of connecting the dots to overcome the difficulties and bridge the gap of learning. With

the demand of the present education, the reading enhancement intervention was designed to walk with students and the kind of special attention on their learning, vis-a-vis with the performance of teachers monitoring the progress of their learners and to improve the methods of teaching.

Fluency. Fluency describes a set of foundational skills that are essential to developing literacy. To say the least, fluency makes reading and as a result, makes learning easier. Students who were fluent in reading will struggle less with difficult words and will comprehend more easily with complex topics.

As reflected in the table, fluency got the average grade of 68.02 interpreted as Emerging. There were changes from the results after intervention program was implemented. During the intervention program and activities in fluency, learners were given passages to read with the corresponding specific time to finish reading the passage. After reading, teachers gave feedbacks and encouragement to the learners especially to those who were not able to finish reading the passage on the specific time given to the learners. It can be inferred that the intervention program and activities implemented were effective.

It was supported by the findings of Crowe (2015), which articulated that feedback given during oral reading improves children's word accuracy, reading comprehension and fluency. Additionally, findings of Agnes, Thembekele and Sive (2021) affirm that the learners' English skills improved a lot because of the reading enhancement interventions. They benefited more from skilled and fluent remedial educators who attend to their individual need.

Comprehension. Comprehension adds meaning to what is read. Reading comprehension happens when texts on a page when interpreted are not just simple words but a world of thoughts and ideas. It makes reading enjoyable, fun, surreal, and informative. It is needed to succeed in school, work, home, and in everyday lives wherever you are.

Comprehension got the lowest average grade of 45.08 and interpreted as coping. Compare to the level of reading comprehension before project REACH, there were also changes in the data. It implied that Project REACH was an evidenced-based strategy and was successful in increasing the scale of the learners reading comprehension skills in terms of word recognition, fluency and comprehension. It can be inferred that reading comprehension skills of the learners may improve if they are engaged in reading intervention program, different reading activities and reading strategies. Learners need to have comprehension in order to be successful academically.

These results coincided with the study of Tadayonifar et al. (2021) which states that students' reading comprehension is significantly enhanced by using detailed guidance on various reading strategies thus, educators must use appropriate reading strategies that are catered to the readers' "perceived learning styles" for readers to improve their reading comprehension and have fun in reading. Intervention programs involving comprehension-building skills, like remedial reading, strengthen vocabulary (McCardle et al., 2021). This method of practice increases language skills and builds general knowledge setting a foundation for basic life skills. Likewise, findings of Amira (2018) states that reading comprehension can be solve by employing variety of reading strategies.

Consequently, based on the study of Acedillo, Nanette and Saro (2023), reading comprehension is essential for future learning and understanding and without it, pupils will struggle academically. It is essential that the learners can comprehend text in an effective manner to succeed in their academic and professional objectives at the global level. Relatedly, the study of Oakhill (2014) stated that a definitive point of perusing is not the interaction however to comprehend what learners read, and cognizance can occur at various levels, it is important for more than just understanding text; it is likewise for general learning, academic success and employment success. On the same point of view, the former secretary of the Department of Education, Bro. Armin A. Luistro (2016) emphasized and stated that evaluating and measuring reading comprehension and competence is the fundamental cornerstone of all academic learning activities. Because of this, learning other disciplines will be a constant battle for the students if they do not grasp reading skill at the outset.

The schema theory supported the study by explaining how readers use prior knowledge to comprehend and learn from text. The fundamental principle of the schema theory assumes that written text does not carry meaning by itself. Rather, a text only provides directions for readers as to how they should retrieve or construct meaning from their own previously acquired knowledge.

Significant Difference on the Reading Comprehension Skills Before and After Project Reach Implementation

Implementation of project REACh is imperative to improve reading comprehension skills, particularly to elementary school learners because word recognition, fluency and comprehension are particularly important at this stage of development and early intervention can impact the progression of reading difficulties. For this reason, the

researcher wanted to determine the significant difference on the reading comprehension skills before and after project REACH implementation.

Table 4 shows the significant difference on the reading comprehension skills before and after project REACH implementation.

Table 4
Significant Difference on the Reading Comprehension of Learners Before and After Project REACH Implementation

	SD	t-value	p-value	Int.
Posttest-Pretest	4.688	-9.482	0.000	S

significant at the 0.05 level

Legend: N – Sample Size
SD – Standard Deviation
I – Interpretation
S – Significant

In the result, it showed that there was significant difference on the reading comprehension skills before and after project REACH implementation, with a t-value of -9.482 and p-value of 0.000. The computed value indicated the difference on the reading comprehension skills of the learners before and after project REACH implementation. Thus, this finding meant that the implementation of project REACH program has remarkably improve the reading comprehension skills of the learners.

Reading program was imperative to improve reading comprehension skills particularly to elementary learners because fluency and comprehension were particularly important at this stage of development and early intervention can impact the progression of reading difficulties.

The study's findings were in consonance with those of Schijns et al. (2020), who discovered that using contextualized learning materials resulted in a very significant difference between the pretest and posttest outcomes. Also, the students' supervision and desire in reading the course materials influenced their reading proficiency (Eshet-Alkalai, 2013; Saro, et al. 2022).

Moreover, Barlette Schema Theory cited by Seymour (2017) states that by letting the learners use their previous skills in reading and remember the phonemic awareness and alphabetic principles. Hence, learners were given learning activities that fir their level. Learners who were in word recognition level, the activities given to them were at this level

also, same as fluency and comprehension. They need first to master word recognition and fluency before they were given activities in reading comprehension. Additionally, Vygotsky suggested that students should be educated where they are capable of learning with peer support, instructional strategies, and regular assessment. Scaffolding involves breaking down complex tasks into smaller, more manageable steps, and providing support and feedback as students work through each step.

Significant Relationship Between the Reading Comprehension Skills after Project REACH was Implemented and the Reading Intervention Design

Project REACH is one of the reading interventions that is thought to have great impact in assisting the learners to improve their reading comprehension skills. Thus, it is in this premise that the researcher decided to conduct this study to evaluate the significant relationship between the reading comprehension skills before and after the implementation of Project REACH. The said relationship was answered through the use of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation of coefficient.

Table 5

Significant Relationship Between Reading Comprehension Skills Before and After Project REACH Implementation

		r-value	Int.	p-value	Int.
Project REACH	Reading Comprehension Skills	0.944	Very High Correlation	0.000	Significant

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Legend:

<i>Computed r-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
<i>Less than +/-0.19</i>	<i>Negligible Correlation</i>
<i>+/-0.20 to +/-0.39</i>	<i>Low Correlation</i>
<i>+/-0.40 to +/-0.69</i>	<i>Moderate Correlation</i>
<i>+/-0.70 to +/-0.89</i>	<i>High Correlation</i>
<i>+/-0.90 to +/-0.99</i>	<i>Very High Correlation</i>
<i>+/-1.00</i>	<i>Perfect Correlation</i>

As reflected in Table 5, the computed value of $r = 0.94$ which implied that there was very high correlation between the comprehension skills before and after project REACH was implemented. The p-value of 0.000 which was less than 0.05 implied that the

relationship was significant. Thus, it can be inferred that the implementation of Project REACH efficiently and effectively improved the reading comprehension skills of the learners.

This was supported by Allington, (2019) who believes that there is a need to match students individually to the intervention that will work best. Wallace (2020) opines that effective reading programs involves teachers modelling for students the abilities they struggle with and guiding students as they practice these skills. Interventions should then focus on teaching students how to use strategies to improve comprehension of texts read. This intervention serves as an avenue for students to develop awareness in the importance of learning World Literature by exploring literary text in a lighter mood for them to catch up in their regular class.

Findings of the study were supported by the Scaffolding Theory which articulated that experts as well as more experienced people around the student, teachers, parents, and even peers at the same class can act as supports. Scaffolding theory is a teaching technique that involves providing support and guidance to students as they learn new concepts or skills. Yet, planned instructional scaffolds are often provided by teachers. Well-constructed Scaffolds optimize student learning, provide a supportive environment as well as facilitating student independence. Scaffolding strategy refers to supporting students to certain extent until the degree of acquiring new skills in an individual basis. Scaffolding lasts not forever, it stops once students were able to do tasks which are beyond their current capabilities. Teacher's comments and feedback provide students with desire to take responsibility of their learning and to create independence from their teachers' continuous care.

Significant Influence of the Project REACH on the Reading Comprehension Skills of the Learner

The significant influence of project REACH to the reading comprehension skills of the learners was further assessed through coefficient of determination (r^2 – value). Thus, the strength of influence was described as Very Strong, Strong, Moderate, Weak and Very Weak.

Table 6

Significant Influence of the Project REACH on the Reading Comprehension Skills of the Learners

		r^2	Int.
Project REACH	Reading Comprehension Skills	0.891	High

Legend:

<i>0.00</i>	<i>No influence</i>
<i>0.00 to 0.19</i>	<i>Very Low</i>
<i>0.20 to 0.39</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>0.40 to 0.69</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
<i>0.70 to 0.89</i>	<i>High</i>
<i>0.90 to 1.00</i>	<i>Very High</i>

Evidently, the obtained r^2 – value of Project REACH to the reading comprehension skills of the learners was 0.891 described as High. The computed value indicated that project REACH has high influence on the reading comprehension skills of the learners. Thus, it can be inferred that project REACH have a strong influence on the reading comprehension of grade 5 learners. It can be inferred that implementation of REACH project impacted or contributed to the performance of the learners' reading comprehension skills. Hence, the struggling readers showed better improvement.

The results have been supported by various studies. Nindy and Kustijono (2017) state that the use of contextualized reading programs has been a potential source to change the learners' reading comprehension skills in the learning process by means of having these resources allow the learners to read and interactively participate in the classroom while also making themselves more comfortable. Moreover, Glenberg (2017) articulated that reading intervention in education setting enables the students to engage in the critical reflection and understanding text and utilize rational in order to generate adequate responses in comprehension. On the same point of view, Larasati, Purwati, and Munir (2019), affirmed that the goal of reading program instruction is to help students do better in school. Reading enhancement interventions offer an excellent opportunity to support remedial students in mastery learning enhancement in reaching the English threshold. Further, Javed (2015) revealed that educators are required to implement educational strategies that promote critical thinking and pre-reading to develop comprehension skills in the students.

Moreover, top-down reading model theory agreed with the study's finding where it contends that reading is driven by meaning and proceeds from whole to part. It is also known as concept-driven model. Based on this theory, efficient reading does not result from the precise perception and identification of all the elements in a word, but from skills in selecting the fewest, most productive cues necessary. They contend that readers have a prior sense of what could be meaningful in the text, based upon their previous experience.

Conclusions

From the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The reading level of the grade 5 learners along word recognition was established; fluency was emerging; and comprehension was coping. Overall reading comprehension level was emerging.
2. The intervention program followed a design.
3. The curricular validity for the reading intervention along face, content and construct was highly valid. The overall curricular validity was also highly valid.
4. The reading comprehension level of the learners along word recognition was established; fluency was emerging; and comprehension was coping. The overall reading comprehension level was emerging.
5. There was a significant difference on the learners' reading comprehension skills before and after project REACH implementation.
6. There was significant relationship between the reading comprehension skills of the learners before and after project REACH was implemented.
7. Project REACH has high influence on the reading comprehension skills of the learners.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were offered:

1. Word recognition skills may be enhanced to improve the level acquired by the learners and eventually be able to use higher order thinking skills. Comprehension should be practiced more by giving the learners reading exercises for them to be exposed using their critical thinking. School Heads may also include remedial instructions in the class program of the teachers.

2. Teachers whose objective is to craft for an intervention program geared towards improving learners' performance should think a design that would produce the targeted outcome.
3. The curriculum writers and assessors may look over every facet of the instructional materials to guarantee that the design will result to its ultimate purpose or objective of improving the learners' reading comprehension skills.
4. Teachers may extend extra time in teaching reading to the struggling readers to improve the reading comprehension skills of the learners. There may be additional practice and exposure to reading activities that can develop their fluency and comprehension skills. Teachers may also be knowledgeable in providing additional learning support materials to the pupils.
5. Teachers may need to be more inventive in using research-tested strategies such as Enhancement program and activities to improve learners' reading comprehension. Conduct free trainings and seminars to the Elementary teachers specifically in crafting intervention program so that they can also be able to address difficulties of the learners inside their respective classes through the crafted intervention program.
6. Teachers should continuously attend more training and seminars on different teaching strategies for better teaching competency. Teachers may also craft an intervention program for the struggling learners and enhancement activities for the advance learners and follow the reading intervention design to attain the desired outcome. School heads should continuously follow-up the implementation of remediation activities and make a constant checking of teacher's remediation notebook.
7. The Department of Education may fully support the continuing professional development of the teachers for them to be equipped with the necessary knowledge needed in teaching specifically techniques and strategies in the delivery of lessons. They may also encourage the teacher to attend trainings and seminars related to the crafting of intervention program/material so that they may have the facility of crafting their own intervention material. The teachers may also utilize the proposed improvement plan formulated.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The nature of the study was explained to the participants that they will be the beneficiaries of the Project Reading Enhancement Activities for school-age Children (REACH) to determine its effects on their reading comprehension skills. They were also informed that their participation in the study had their parent' consent.

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